

REVISITING BASTI SAMMILANA VIDHI: SYSTEMATIC ANALYSIS WITH SCIENTIFIC APPROACH BEHIND AYURVEDIC ENEMA FORMULATION

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ABSTRACT

Basti Sammilana Vidhi, the process of adding ingredients of *Niruha Basti* in particular sequence according to classics plays crucial role in establishing efficacy and stability of formulation. This article reviews classical Ayurvedic texts *Caraka Samhita*, *Sushruta Samhita*, *Ashtanga Hridaya* and *Kashyapa Samhita* to analyse the sequence and proportion of *Basti* ingredients like *Madhu*, *Saindava*, *Sneha*, *Kalka*, *Kashaya* and *Avapa Dravya*. Each component contributes uniquely- *Madhu* acts as a catalyst, salt aids absorption, lipids improve bioavailability, *Kalka* enhances viscosity and synergy, *Kashaya* delivers water-soluble actives and *Avapa Dravya* adjust potency. A modern interpretation reveals its role in enhancing gut health, mucosal healing and systemic action. Improper mixing can alter absorption and therapeutic results. Understanding and applying correct methodology of *Sammilana Vidhi* is essential for

achieving predictable and effective outcomes of *Basti* therapy.

KEYWORDS: *Niruha Basti*, *Sammilana vidhi*, *Madhu*, *Saindhava*, *Sneha*, *Kalka*, *Kashaya*.

INTRODUCTION

Basti is one among five principal procedures of *Panchakarma* and considered most effective therapy for management of *Vata* disorders. It plays significant role not only in treating disease but also in health maintenance and rejuvenation. Among multiple components of

<i>Kapha</i>	<i>Kshara, Gomutra</i>
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Table No. 3: Shows the quantity of *Basti* According to Different Authors.

Ingredients	<i>Caraka</i>	<i>Sushruta</i>	<i>Vagbhata</i>	<i>Kashyapa</i>
Total Quantity	12 <i>Prasruta</i>	12 <i>Prasruta</i>	9 <i>Prasruta</i>	12 <i>Prasruta</i>
<i>Madhu</i>	2 <i>Prasruta.</i>	4 <i>Phala</i>	3 <i>Phala</i>	2 <i>Phala.</i>
<i>Saindava</i>	1 <i>Karsha.</i>	1 <i>Aksha</i>	½ <i>Karsha.</i>	½ <i>Karsha.</i>
<i>Sneha</i>	2 <i>Prasruta.</i>	6 <i>Phala</i>	3 <i>Phala</i>	4 <i>Phala</i>
<i>Kalka</i>	1 <i>Prasruta.</i>	2 <i>Phala.</i>	2 <i>Phala.</i>	2 <i>Phala.</i>
<i>Kashaya</i>	5 <i>Prasruta</i>	4 <i>Phala.</i>	5 <i>Prasruta</i>	4 <i>Phala.</i>
<i>Avapa</i>	1 <i>Prasruta</i>	4 <i>Phala</i>	1 <i>Prasruta</i>	2 <i>Phala.</i>

Modern Interpretation

HONEY

Honey helps in enhanced therapeutic outcomes by modulating gut micro biota and promoting the production of short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs) such as butyrate. SCFAs support colonic health by serving as an energy source for colonocytes, strengthening the intestinal barrier, promoting mucus and tight junction protein production and reducing inflammation. They also help regulate immune responses by increasing regulatory T cells and suppressing pro-inflammatory cytokines like Interleukin-17.

SALT

Saindhava Lavana plays critical role as functional adjuvant. Salt enhances osmolarity of *Basti Dravya*, promoting water movement into colon by osmosis. This property helps to soften stool, eases its evacuation and facilitate the spread of medication across mucosal surface. It also improves solubility and dispersion of lipid-based or hydrophobic components like oils and ghee, ensuring uniform consistency and bioavailability of active compounds. Its mild irritant action of salt can stimulate peristalsis and reflex evacuation. Its known antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory properties may also contribute to gut mucosal healing.

LIPIDS

Lipid components play crucial supportive role in maintaining gut integrity and enhancing therapeutic efficacy. They help to repair epithelial damage, strengthen intestinal barrier and support a balanced gut micro biome. Lipids also soften stools and ease defecation and their emollient nature minimizes colonic irritation during administration. Additionally, lipids nourish enteric nervous system, aiding autonomic regulation. These also improve the

solubility and absorption of fat-soluble herbal constituents, enhancing bioavailability and promoting faster systemic action by bypassing hepatic metabolism.

KALKA

Kalka imparts the desired viscosity to *Basti* formulation ensuring proper consistency for effective administration. It functions as a bio-enhancer, amplifying the therapeutic potential of other components. By promoting better mucosal adherence and absorption, *Kalka* supports localized action and may facilitate synergistic interactions among active ingredients, thereby enhancing the overall efficacy of *Basti* formulation.

KASHAYA

Kashaya contains water-soluble Phyto-constituents such as Alkaloids, Tannins, Glycosides and Flavonoids. These bioactive compounds are effectively absorbed through colonic mucosa, contributing to systemic therapeutic effects. They help to stimulate peristalsis, aid in elimination of toxins and impacted faecal matter and regulate Gut micro biota and fermentation processes. The aqueous nature of *Kashaya* enhances hydration and may assist in correcting electrolyte imbalance. These constituents exhibit anti-inflammatory, antioxidant and immunomodulatory properties offering both local and systemic benefits.

DISCUSSION

The efficacy of *Niruha Basti* is due to its ingredients as well as by methodology of their combination- *Basti Sammilana Vidhi*. Classical texts provide a detailed, stepwise methodology for the mixing process designed to enhance physicochemical and therapeutic properties of formulation. This discussion integrates textual review with contemporary scientific perspectives to highlight the critical relevance of this method.

The sequence of mixing *Madhu*, *Saindhava*, *Sneha*, *Kalka*, *Kashaya* and *Avapa Dravya*- is not arbitrary but reflects a systematic strategy for achieving stable and bioactive formulation. The initial use of *Madhu* acts as a bio-enhancer and emulsifying agent that improves the miscibility of aqueous and lipid phases. It's prebiotic and SCFA-inducing properties support gut mucosal integrity and systemic immune modulation. *Saindhava* further aids in osmotic balance, enhances solubilisation and stimulates colonic peristalsis, aligning with modern understanding of osmotic laxatives and mucosal stimulants. *Sneha* contributes not just to uniformity but significantly to the absorption of lipophilic actives, epithelial repair and neuro-immune regulation within enteric system. These functions are critical in the context of *Vata*

disorders which primarily affect neurological and musculoskeletal systems. *Kalka*, traditionally seen as a viscosity enhancer, also serves as a synergistic bioactive carrier. It may extend the retention time of formulation, aid in local therapeutic action and improve mucosal contact-all of which are important for drug absorption in rectal therapy. *Kashaya*, rich in water-soluble phytochemicals brings therapeutic specificity to the formulation. Modern phytochemical analysis of such decoctions reveals anti-inflammatory, antioxidant and immunomodulatory effects, supporting their use in inflammatory bowel conditions, systemic detoxification and modulation of gut micro biota. The role of *Avapa Dravya*, though auxiliary, is crucial for titrating the potency and fluidity of preparation. Their adaptogenic and catalytic properties influence the penetration and speed of *Basti* action. Importantly, deviations in the classical *Sammilana* sequence or technique may lead to phase separation, loss of active constituents, poor mucosal absorption and ultimately less assured therapeutic results. This highlights the need for precise procedural adherence in clinical practice to ensure reproducibility and consistent outcomes.

Integrating traditional Ayurvedic rationale with current pharmacological insights validates ancient methodology and underscores the need for its rigorous application. Furthermore, this bridge between classical wisdom and contemporary science offers a foundation for developing standardized yet personalized enema therapies, particularly valuable in chronic *Vata* disorders, metabolic dysfunctions and autoimmune conditions.

CONCLUSION

Basti Sammilana Vidhi is a critical stage in the preparation of *Niruha Basti* directly influencing its therapeutic efficacy and stability. Classical texts outline a specific order of mixing ingredients to ensure synergy, uniformity and optimal absorption. Modern interpretations support these principles, revealing how components like honey, salt, lipids and herbal decoctions promote mucosal healing, enhance bioavailability and modulate immune responses. Deviating from the prescribed method can compromise effectiveness of formulations. Therefore, precise adherence to *Basti Sammilana Vidhi* is essential for achieving consistent clinical outcomes and integrating traditional Ayurvedic practices with modern therapeutic insights.

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